

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION

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Annotation. This article explores the role of artificial intelligence in education and its growing impact. It discusses several AI-powered platforms and explains how they help students to learn individually as well as reduce teachers workload. It also highlights advantages and challenges of an artificial intelligence. Overall, this article provides balanced overview of how AI can improve system of education when used responsibly and correctly.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellektning ta'limdagi o'rni va uning o'sib borayotgan ta'siri haqida o'ganiladi. Unda bir nechta sun'iy intellekt bilan quvvatlangan platformalar muhokama qilinadi va ular qanday qilib o'quvchilarning mustaqil o'qishida yordam berishi hamda o'qituvchilarning ishi yukini kamaytirishida yordam berishini tushuntiriladi. Shuningdek, sun'iy intellektning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari ta'kidlangan. Umuma olganda, ushbu maqola mas'uliyat bilan va to'g'ri foydalanilganda sun'iy intellekt ta'lim tizimii qanday yaxshilashi mumkinligi haqida muvozanatli ma'lumot beradi.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается роль искусственного интеллекта в образовании и его растущее влияние. В ней рассматриваются несколько платформ, основанных на искусственном интеллекте, и объясняется, как они помогают учащимся учиться индивидуально, а также снижают нагрузку на учителей. Также освещаются преимущества и проблемы искусственного интеллекта. В целом, эта статья дает сбалансированный обзор того, как искусственный интеллект может улучшить систему образования при ответственном и правильном использовании

Key words: Artificial intelligence, education, ai-powered platforms, benefits, challenges, online website, personalized learning, quick feedbacks, privacy risk, inaccurate information, efficiency, algorithm

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, ta'lim, sun'iy intellekt bilan quvvatlangan platformalar, afzalliklar, kamchiliklar, onlayn veb- sayt, shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim, tezkor fikr- mulohaza, maxfiylik xavfi, noto'g'ri ma'lumot, samadorlik, algoritm.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, образование, платформы на базе ИИ, преимущества, проблемы, онлайн-сайт, персонализированное обучение, быстрые отзывы, риск конфиденциальности, неточная информация, эффективность, алгоритм.

In recent years, artificial intelligence(AI) began to become popular in many aspects, as well as in education. AI is computer program that can perform almost any task a human can do, for example learning data analyzing and making decisions. In education AI is widely used to support teachers, enhance overall efficiency of learning.

Furthermore, numerous AI- powered platforms has emerged. For instance, **Khan Academy**, an app which helps students to learn different subjects, such as mathematics, science, language learning, even life skills. This program gives instant feedbacks on student's performance, suggests topics to review and focuses on areas where they need improvement. Similarly, **Duolingo**, uses highly developed AI systems to improve students experiences ([Bicknell et al., 2023](#)). The platform offers courses for more than 40 languages. It adjusts the difficulty of

exercises to learner's knowledge level and performance, making it accessible for everyone. Specializing in smart grading solutions, **iFlyTek** provides technology optimized for various academic settings, most notably for China's high-stakes National College Entrance Examination (Gaokao) ([iFlyTeK, 2024](#)). An app launched in early 2024 by 2 brothers called **Turbo AI** has been helping students in various ways. One of them is note-taking which many students struggle to do, by uploading the lecture student will receive notes as well as flashcards, quizzes to memorise the theme. Additionally, with over 8000 quick lessons **ELSA Speak** app helps non-natives to speak in English with confidence. An AI coach in the platform is designed to improve English pronunciation, fluency, grammar and speaking level of learners. ([Xabibullayeva Zarina, 2025](#))

As we know, grading is the most time-consuming part of teaching ([Reid Sczebra, 2019](#)), so online website called Gradescope is highly used to grade students assignments and exams by teachers of all subjects ([Reid Sczebra, 2019](#)). The platform not only grades, but also analyzes student's work, which gives clear understanding to both student and teacher. **Turnitin**, on the other hand, is plagiarism detector, mostly used while checking articles and essays, which is effective tool to maintain academic honesty. Moreover, AI bots like **ChatGPT** and **Gemini** can be a key to stop repetition, by giving new teaching methods, plans, games to make the class more interactive, also can be used to make online tests, quizzes and exercises.

One main advantage of AI, it can be used to personalize learning by adapting the content to student's needs and style of learning ([Office of Communications, 2024](#)), which teachers can not, as not all students understanding speed, path is same. So studying with AI-powered platforms consistently will encourage and motivate the student to learn more. For instance, **Duolingo** tends to attract its learners by this method, as well as its daily streaks, leaderboards.

Furthermore, providing student instant and detailed feedback about their learning process, performance helps learners to see their weaknesses and strengths ([Office of Communications, 2024](#)). Compared to teachers, AI is more reliable since it has huge academic base and works with algorithm.

Lastly, through AI-powered platforms like **Turbo AI**, **ChatGPT**, **Gemini** and **Gamma**, both students and teachers can create study materials such as lessons, activities, games, flashcards, quizzes, presentations by providing short explanation or key words ([Office of Communications, 2024](#)).

With all the benefits that AI offers to teachers and students, it does come with some drawback and challenges. First of all, privacy and security concerns. It has been a worry of lots of people since AI has been around ([Office of Communications, 2024](#)). People are anxious about it because they do not know whether their personal information is safe or not. Some even fear it being leaked and exposed to public, which causes crimes like identity theft, scamming as well as threatening.

The next drawback is reduction of human interactions. Relying more on AI will automatically decrease teacher-student interactions and relationship ([Office of Communications, 2024](#)), causing to slow or stop the development of student's social-emotional skill and critical communication ability.

Perhaps one of the most concerning issue is unpredictability and inaccurate information. AI is only as good as the algorithms included ([Office of Communications, 2024](#)). If a question out of its data, it is most likely to give incorrect or biased answer. **ChatGPT** is an obvious example for this, especially if a learner gives a question in foreign languages like Uzbek. So it is better to use trustworthy educational websites to get an accurate answer.

In addition, **UNESCO** developed **AI competency frameworks for students and teachers**. Its aim is to generate an understanding about the opportunities as well as risks that AI offers in education(unesco.org).

Artificial Intelligence has a potential to transform education by making it more personalized, efficient and accessible. Risks and challenges of using it, however, should also be taken into consideration as overconfidence in AI feedback and information may not always be accurate.

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